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PROSTHETICS WITH REMOVABLE PROSTHESES IN PATIENTS WITH EDEMA OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE PROSTHETIC FIELD

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Abstract

Recently, there has been an increase in the number of patients with a complete absence of teeth and complaints of deterioration in the stabilization of complete removable dentures during the day. The main reason for unsatisfactory fixation of prostheses is periodic swelling of the oral mucosa due to impaired kidney function and pathology of the cardiovascular system. In this regard, it is necessary to obtain impressions taking into account the degree of edema of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, which will improve the functional characteristics and stabilization of complete removable dentures, reduce the number of corrections and significantly reduce the adaptation period.

Keywords: complete secondary adentia, edema of the oral mucosa, prosthetics.

The problem of complete loss of teeth and prosthetics with removable dentures remains relevant today. In the general structure of the population in need of removable prosthetics, persons with a complete absence of teeth make up about 35–40% [1,2, 3], and the need for the manufacture of complete removable dentures tends to increase. According to WHO, for various reasons, up to 26 % of patients with complete loss of teeth cannot use the manufactured plate prostheses due to their unsatisfactory fixation [4, 5,6], which leads to a decrease in social activity of people and a deterioration in their quality of life [6]. This is due to a number of factors, among which an important role is played by the oral mucosa [7]. The use of implants for prosthetics is quite expensive and is not always shown, which makes them unaffordable for most patients. In the last 10 years, the number of patients with complaints about changes in the stabilization of complete removable dentures during the day has increased: it worsens in the morning or after lunch. At the same time, some patients complain of a “tight” prosthesis in the morning or in the afternoon, which then becomes “wide” and is poorly fixed. All these complaints increase the number of corrections of the manufactured prostheses, as a result of which their stabilization worsens, which leads to serious violations of the adaptation process. Often, patients

continue to use old prostheses, not because of their aesthetic and functional shortcomings [8]. The current methods of re-prosthetics in severe jaw atrophy are primarily aimed at creating maximum comfort from the use of complete removable dentures [9, 10]. In our opinion, today they do not pay due attention to the study of the frequency of unsatisfactory fixation of complete removable dentures in patients with somatic diseases who have different degrees of swelling of the oral mucosa and they change during the day.

The aim of the study is to improve the quality of fixation of prostheses in patients with complete loss of teeth and periodic edema of the oral mucosa caused by chronic renal failure of cardiac origin, by rationalizing the method of obtaining functional impressions for the manufacture of complete removable dentures.

Material and research methods

To achieve the goals and objectives set in the work, 30 patients aged 55 to 70 years who had mucosal edema and complained of poor fixation of complete removable dentures during the day were examined. In this regard, there was a need for additional examination of such patients with an in-depth study of concomitant diseases [11] and the state of the mucosa.

To establish the time interval in which the oral mucosa had an "average" degree of edema, old or tempo-

rary prostheses were used with their hourly fixation assessment as: good (3 points), satisfactory (2 points) and unsatisfactory (1 point). After a thorough examination, patients were referred for a consultation with general practitioners, endocrinologists, and nephrologists, depending on the nature of concomitant diseases, for their subsequent complex treatment. Depending on the results of in-depth studies of specialized specialists, the effectiveness of treatment and the clinical course of general somatic diseases, the possibility of subsequent orthopedic treatment was established.

Research results

At the first stage, time-based registration of the stabilization of old or temporary complete removable dentures was performed for 1 week. The time interval was determined when the patient did not complain and the prosthesis had the best fixation, characterized as an "average degree" of edema of the prosthetic bed mucosa.

The best fixation of prostheses was observed from 11 o'clock morning to 1 pm and in the evening from 5 pm to 7 pm. Based on these data, we obtained anatomical and functional impressions for the manufacture of new complete dentures, and also carried out the stages of fitting an individual tray and the application of complete dentures at noon and in the evening. However, the monitoring showed that in some patients the degree of edema changed not only hourly, but also during the week. For such patients, we recommended prosthetics only after additional courses of treatment of the underlying disease and stabilization of the excretory function of the kidneys.

The data of the clinical study showed the high efficiency of the proposed method for obtaining functional imprints: in 24 (80%) patients, the stabilization of the fabricated prostheses was good or satisfactory, and in 6 (20%) cases, unsatisfactory, which can be explained by excessive atrophy of the jaws in elderly patients. In such cases, we recommended additional surgical preparation of the tissues of the prosthetic bed.

Conclusions

1. A positive result of prosthetics in elderly patients with complete secondary edentulism and poor clinical conditions depends on the accuracy of reproduction of the relief of the mucosa of the prosthetic bed

2. The optimal time for taking impressions and corrections in patients with periodic swelling of the oral mucosa due to chronic renal failure of cardiac origin is the second half of the day.

3. Hourly diagrams of the quality of prosthesis fixation for several days of observation should match for each patient. Otherwise, rational prosthetics is recommended only after additional courses of complex treatment of concomitant pathology.

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